

FIC Fighters

From Waste to Sustainable Products

FIC-Fighters in a nutshell

- FIC-Fighters is an **EU-funded project** advancing sustainable solutions for managing phosphogypsum (PG) waste while supporting the circular economy.
- By involving local stakeholders and industries, we aim to **transform PG waste into valuable raw materials** for sectors like paper, cement, batteries, fertilisers, and detergents.
- Performing research across six European sites, FIC-Fighters focuses on achieving **Technology Readiness Level 6-7 for waste recovery processes**.
- Our project fosters interdisciplinary collaboration and promotes innovative practices to regenerate PG stacks, reducing environmental impacts and **supporting sustainable urban development**.

Valorisation of phosphogypsum wastes into commercial products to achieve **healthy cities** through **sustainable and circular processes**.

Our main objectives

Over 48 months, in collaboration with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), FIC-Fighters will:

- **Build a Mobile Pilot Plant**
- **Create a Phosphogypsum Forum**
- **Enhance Flexibility and Replicability**
- **Establish a Knowledge Exchange Forum**
- **Provide Circularity Guidelines**

Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative

 fic-fighters.eu

Funded by
the European Union

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